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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

ACHITQI ZAMBURUG‘LARINING LABORATORIYA SHAROITIDA O‘RGANISH USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Achitqi zamburug‘lari (*Saccharomyces*) — bir hujayrali eukaryot organizmlar bo‘lib, asosan *Ascomycota* bo‘limiga mansub. Ular tabiiy muhitda keng tarqalgan bo‘lib, oziq-ovqat sanoati, biotexnologiya, farmatsevtika va genetik tadqiqotlarda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Achitqi zamburug‘lari fermentatsiya jarayonlari orqali spirtli ichimliklar, non mahsulotlari, antibiotiklar va boshqa biotexnologik mahsulotlarning ishlab chiqarilishida asosiy rol o‘ynaydi.

Tabiiy mahsulotlarga bo‘lgan talab ortib borayotgani sababli, mikroorganizmlardan, jumladan, achitqilardan yangi oziq-ovqat ingredientlari va qo‘shimchalar (masalan, rang beruvchilar, antioksidantlar va vitaminlar) ishlab chiqarish manbasi sifatida foydalanish tobora dolzarb bo‘lib bormoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: achitqi zamburug‘lari, Vitamin, Penitsillin va streptomitsin, Lui Paster tajribasi, *sachomitsess serviziya*

Achitqi zamburug‘lari bir hujayrali mikroorganizmlar bo‘lib, shakli yumaloq yoki oval bo‘ladi. Ularning hujayra devori polisaxaridlar (glukan va mannan), xitin va oqsillardan iborat. Hujayralari mitoxondriyalar, ribosomalar, yadro va vakuolalar bilan ajralib turadi. Eukariyot bo‘lgani uchun yadro membranasi mavjud va DNK xromosomalar shaklida bo‘ladi. Hayot sikli va ko‘payishiga ko‘ra achitqi zamburug‘lari ikkita asosiy usulda ko‘payadi: Vegetativ (nospora) ko‘payish ya‘ni tomchi bo‘linish (pupillash) – asosiy ko‘payish usuli. Ona hujayradan kichik qiz hujayra ajralib chiqadi. Noqulay sharoitlarda diploid hujayralar mitoz yo‘li bilan sporalar hosil qiladi. Sporalar mos muhitda o‘sganda, gaploid hujayralarga aylanadi va juftlashib yana diploid hujayraga aylanishi mumkin. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* va *Saccharomyces ellipsoideus* kabi turlari spirtli fermentatsiya orqali uglevodlarni etanol(C_2H_5OH) va karbonat angidrid (CO_2) ga aylantiradi. $C_6H_{12}O_6 \rightarrow 2C_2H_5OH + 2CO_2$

Achitqilar iste‘molchilar orasida ijobiy obro‘ga ega bo‘lgani sababli, ular oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini qayta ishlash uchun xavfsiz ingredient va qo‘shimchalar manbai sifatida qaraladi. Nonvoylik va pivo xamirturushlari ko‘p yillar davomida “B” vitaminlari, oqsillar, peptidlar, aminokislotalar va mikroelementlarga boyligi sababli parhez va ozuqaviy qo‘shimchalar sifatida foydalanib kelinmoqda.

Non achitish jarayonida achitqilar kraxmal va shakarni parchalab, karbonat angidrid hosil qiladi. Xamirning ko‘tarilishiga yordam berib, yumshoq va g‘ovak tuzilish hosil qiladi. Kefir, yogurt kabi mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishda ba‘zi achitqi turlari laktobakteriyalar bilan birga ishlatiladi.

Spirтли bijg'ish jarayoni tirik organizmlar ishtirokida borishini, ya'ni biologik jarayonlar ekanligini 1858—yil Lui Paster aniqlagan. Bu davrgacha spirтли bijg'ish jarayoni kimyoviy reaksiyalardan iborat xodisa deb qaralgan xolos. Achitqi zamburug'lari fakultativ anaerob organizmlar qatoriga kiradi, lekin aerob sharoitda ham hayot kechira oladi. Achitqi zamburug'ining aerob sharoitdagi hayot faoliyati natijasida shakarning ko'p qismi suv va sirka kislotagacha parchalanadi. Bunda spirt kam hosil bo'ladi. Achitqi zamburug'ini mikroskopda ko'rish uchun oddiy pivo achitqisidan yoki quruq hamirturush suvda eziladi va eritiladi. Artib sterillangan buyum oynasiga bakterial ilmoq yordamida eritmadan bir tomchi tomizilib, usti qoplag'ich oyna bilan yopiladi. Mikroskopda ko'rish uchun immersion moy tomizilib, katta obyektiv orqali qaraladi. Mikroskopda oval shakldagi *saxromitsess serviziya* ko'rindi.

Xulosa:

Achitqi zamburug'lari oziq-ovqat sanoati, fermentatsiya jarayonlari, biotexnologiya va farmatsevtika sohalorida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ularning biokimyoviy xususiyatlari, genetik o'zgaruvchanligi va fermentativ faolligi turli sohalarda qo'llanilishiga imkon beradi. Kelajakda achitqi zamburug'lari biologik yoqilg'ilar, sun'iy oziq-ovqatlar, genetik terapiya kabi yo'nalishlarda yanada keng qo'llanilishi kutilmoqda.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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